

Beyond the Quantum – From Self- Organization to Consciousness

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1. Quantum Mechanics Successes and Achievements

Over the last twenty years or so, there has been a decrease in number of students enrolling in physics course worldwide. Academics, educational and businesses communities have offered various solutions to the current crisis. The decrease in students learning physics is the results of a number of factors, and researchers argue that physics no longer enjoys the limelight it enjoyed for many years. On the other hand, biology has become a more attractive branch of science as students are uncertain about whether job opportunities will be open to them if they pursue physics. Furthermore, physics lecturers are unable to give knowledgeable and helpful career advice. Others argue that the typical university physics program is too theoretical and does not produce graduate with skills and knowledge that employers expect. Finally, physics is seen as a complex, abstract and mathematics intensive reserved for an intellectual elite of aspiring Einstein.

Perhaps is the time has come to remind students, economists and the public of the amazing contribution of physics to our modern society. There is no doubt that the entire world economy is linked to technologies such as computer, transistor, laser or the World Wide Web, all of which were invented by physicists. Physical research has benefited and continues to benefit our modern world and economy. Without physics, there would not be the so-called high-tech industries, which resulted in the creation of millions of high-paying jobs. Physics has thus contributed to alleviate poverty, diseases, and above all, has been partially responsible for the industrial revolution.

Likewise, the progress made by the countries of the Western world, Asia and some African countries, is largely linked to the ability to embrace modern technologies. Today, the banal transistor is found in almost all electronics apparatus and computers. In other words, without a branch of physics called quantum mechanics, we would not be talking about the global economy or the information age. Indeed, many areas of science have benefited from quantum mechanics. Advances in chemistry, electronics, genetics, biology and other related sciences could not have happened without a deep understanding of the atoms. Quantum mechanics has been successful in application to astronomy, cosmology, chemistry, biology, biochemistry, etc. In astronomy, we can only understand nuclear reaction in the sun based on quantum mechanical principles.

Without quantum mechanics, we would not have witnessed the electronics revolution that has brought us the

internet. In fact, quantum mechanics has laid the foundations for the entire communications and information industries. This technological revolution includes the development of radio-transistor, television, computer chip, grocery-store laser, credit-card hologram, nuclear power, etc. Key inventions such as the laser are due to quantum mechanics. Laser technology is widely used in the area of medicine, telecommunication, agriculture, manufacturing industry, road and safety. In medicine, lasers are used to detect and cure condition such as cataracts, glaucoma, tuberculosis and various forms of cancer. Thanks to the internet, education has been transformed and a new generation of e-learners is growing up with dramatically increased powers of learning as technology enables knowledge in ways that are perfectly tailored to individual needs. In summary, almost all modern technologies are based on quantum understanding of semi-conductor and molecular phenomena. To some extent, all branches of sciences have benefited from quantum physics, so much that we can conclude that without quantum mechanics, there would never have been a global economy. Here is a brief list of successes as well as phenomena that quantum mechanics can explain:

- The photoelectric effect,
- The spectrum of liquid, solid and gas,
- The scanning tunnelling microscope,
- Black-body radiation in terms of quantization,
- Bizarre phenomena such as superconductivity, super-fluidity and Bose-Einstein condensates,
- How chemical forces which hold molecules together.

2. Beyond the Quantum

Despite the many successes of quantum mechanics, a minority within the physics community feels unease and has loudly expressed their discomfort. There are unresolved foundational questions, the measurement problem, wave particle duality, non-local effects, etc. This feeling arises when one realizes that quantum mechanics implies a number of counter-intuitive notions. This has led such a great physicist as Niels Bohr to comment, “Anyone who is not shocked by the quantum mechanics theory does not understand it!” In the same vein, Roger Penrose exclaimed: “Something new will have to come in and change the structure of quantum mechanics.”

Along the same reasoning, Detlef and Durr tell us that while quantum mechanics provides us with formalism, it does not attempt to provide a description of reality. Almost all physicists agree upon the correctness of the formalism which is well supported by experimental evidence. However, the description behind the reality remains controversial, so much that there are many interpretations of the theory. For instance, British physicist Roger Penrose is full of praise for the achievements of quantum, but he also stresses that it has many ‘unsolved mysteries. There are mysteries of two different kinds, he argues, the Z and X mysteries. This view is

also supported by many physicists including (Silverman, 1995) and (Anton Zeilinger, 1999).

Over the last few years, many alternatives to statistical quantum mechanics have been proposed. Digital Physics is a possible candidate and might perhaps offer a viable alternative and encompass quantum theory and accounts for its successes and achievements, but above all makes more sense.

Digital Physics is the study of discrete models for physics. Digital Physics combines quantum mechanics, thermodynamics, information theory, and some aspects of theoretical computer science. Discrete physical models are alternatives to continuous or partially continuous models. Physics uses continuous models to compress reality into formulae in order to build a mathematical models or theories that explain phenomena taking place within our universe. Model such as the Schrödinger equation is formulated in the continuous language of differential equations. Space and time are thought as continuous. In discrete models, space is treated as a lattice, and time is discrete. From a theoretical standpoint, argues (Erik Rauch, 2001), such models have the advantage that they do not have infinitely many locations. From a practical standpoint, they correspond to the discrete structure of digital computing machines and this makes them natural for simulations.

Physics teaches us that every object we touch or see is made up of matter and that all matter is made up of atoms. In turn, atoms are made up of particles: electrons, protons, neutrons, etc. However, recent advances in the physics of information reveal that the universe may also be composed of bits (binary digits) of information. Programming the Universe, (Seth Lloyd, 06) shows how the universe can be described as a giant computer. According to Seth Lloyd, every atom and elementary particles expresses these bits, and every collision between those atoms and particles flips the bits into a new arrangement and effortlessly spins out complex and beautiful systems, including galaxies, planets, and life itself.

Despite considerable academic interest in the area of discrete physics (“the computing paradigm”), to date only limited research exists on this subject. Many scholars have become increasingly dissatisfied with the current continuous model and are looking for an alternative to statistical quantum mechanics. My research would address the following intriguing questions:

- Why is quantum mechanics such a difficult subject?
- How do you resolve all of the paradoxes and puzzle mysteries of quantum mechanics?
- Does the wave function provide a complete description of physical reality?
- Electrons behave sometimes like particles and sometimes likes waves; how can this be possible?
- Is it possible that an alternative theory such as Bohmian mechanics could provide an answer to the mysteries and paradoxes of quantum theory?
- Is information more fundamental than matter and energy?

- Is it possible that time and everything in space-time is discrete and can be modelled by discrete values (integers)?

Together, these questions are aimed at developing a deeper understanding of the mysteries and paradoxes of quantum mechanics. To examine these issues, I will review past conceptual, empirical research and new promising ideas on possible solutions as I discuss why a new physics is needed. In spite of its successes and achievements, quantum mechanics finds itself in a condition of foundational crisis, facing problems of philosophical, conceptual, and technical nature. What we now call Digital Physics might perhaps offer a viable alternative...

3. References

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